

Synthesis of mercury-, tin-, lead- and zinc(II) complexes with a tetradentate Schiff base 1,2-glyoxilidene-bis-2-aminoethylpyridine

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Manuscript received 5 March 2003, revised 2 August 2003, accepted 19 February 2004

Some new complexes of Hg^{II}, Sn^{II}, Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} of the type [MX₂L] (where X = Cl, Br and L = tetradentate Schiff base 1,2-glyoxilidene-bis-2-aminoethylpyridine) have been synthesised and characterised physico-chemically.

The Schiff bases obtained from dicarbonilic compounds are able to coordinate to metallic ions in different ways¹. In this category are included the complexes with the Schiff bases obtained from glyoxal; for example, the complexes with tetradentate Schiff bases of the type (ONNO) obtained by condensation of glyoxal and *o*-aminophenol or anthranilic acid and their adducts with basic molecules having nitrogen as donor (pyridine, imidazol etc.)². The molecular model shows that the ligand coordinates via two N and two O atoms and form square-planar complexes. In certain conditions, it is possible to obtain polynuclear coordination compounds with unusual structures and magnetic properties, using the capability of phenoxo groups to act as bridges³.

This paper deals with the synthesis and characterizations of some complexes with Hg^{II}, Sn^{II}, Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} of tetradentate Schiff base ligands of the type (NNNN) i.e. 1,2-glyoxilidene-bis-2-aminoethylpyridine (GAEPy) (Fig. 1).

Results and discussion

The newly synthesised complexes (Table 1) are stable at RT even on long standing. The low molar conductance values of the complexes in acetone (20–30 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) indicate that they are non-electrolytes⁴.

IR spectrum of the ligand showed two bands at 1634 and 1595 cm⁻¹, which are due to ν_{C=N} from pyridine ring and azomethinic groups⁵, respectively. In these complexes the first band red shifted while the second band blue shifted. This proves that the ligand coordinates to metal ions through the nitrogen atoms of the pyridine rings and azomethinic groups. All the bands showed bands at 405–495 cm⁻¹ (M–X).

The photoelectron peaks binding energies data of all metal ions, M2p_{3/2}, C12p, Br2p and N1s for ligand, MX₂ (M = Sn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II} and Hg^{II}, X = Cl, Br) and [MX₂L] complexes are listed in Table 1. It may be seen that M2p_{3/2} photoelectron peak binding energy values were observed more in metal salts than in metal complexes. It suggests that metal ions have more electron density in metal complexes than metal salts due to involvement of metal ion in the coordination⁶.

Furthermore, N1s photoelectron peak have shown very high binding values in all these metal complexes than ligand nitrogen atom (Table 1) with a single symmetrical N1s photoelectron peak. From these M2p_{3/2} and N1s XPS data one can conclude that all four nitrogen atoms of Schiff base ligands are coordinated to metal ions⁶. The C12p and Br2p photoelectron spectra of all the complexes have shown more BE values in the range of 21.2–201.4 eV (for C12p) and 183.2–183.8 eV (for Br2p) than the starting material which suggest in all the metal complexes chloride ion or bromide ion is coordinated in the inner coordination sphere of metal ion⁶ (Table 1).

Fig. 1. 1,2-Glyoxilidene-bis-2-aminoethylpyridine (GAEPy).

Table I. M2p, N1s, and X2p binding energies (eV) in ligand, MX₂ and [MX₂L] complex

Compd [*]	M2p	N1s	C12p	Bi 3p _{3/2}
Ligand	-	400.2	-	-
HgCl ₂	677.6	-	201.2	-
[HgCl ₂ L]	676.4	401.8	201.2	-
HgBr ₂	677.4	-	-	183.2
[HgBr ₂ L]	676.2	401.8	-	183.2
ZnCl ₂	87.8	-	201.2	-
[ZnCl ₂ L]	85	401.8	201.2	-
ZnBr ₂	87.6	-	-	183.8
[ZnBr ₂ L]	86.4	402	-	183.6
SnCl ₂	715.8	-	202	-
[SnCl ₂ L]	713.8	401.8	201.4	-
SnBr ₂	715.6	-	-	183.6
[SnBr ₂ L]	713.4	402	-	183.6
PbCl ₂	764.8	-	201.4	-
[PbCl ₂ L]	762.0	402.2	201.4	-
PbBr ₂	764.4	-	-	183.8
[PbBr ₂ L]	763.4	402	-	183.8

All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses

Experimental

All reagents, metal salts and organic solvents used were of A.R. grade

Synthesis of the ligand⁷: To a methanolic solution (10 ml) of glyoxal (1 mmol), was added a methanolic solution (10 ml) of 2-aminoethylpyridine (2 mmol). The mixture was stirred for 1 h and then ether was added. The resulting brown solid was washed with ether and dried in a desiccator over H₂SO₄, m.p. > 250°.

Synthesis of the complexes: To a methanolic solution (10 ml) of glyoxal (1 mmol), was added a methanolic solution (10 ml) of 2-aminoethylpyridine (2 mmol). The mixture was stirred for 15 min, then the methanolic solution (10 ml) of metal salts (1 mmol) (MX₂ = ZnCl₂ or HgCl₂ or SnCl₂ or PbCl₂) was added. The solution was refluxed for 6

h, concentrated to half of its volume, ether was added and the resulting solid was washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure

IR spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer. The molar conductivity of 10⁻³ solutions in acetone were obtained on a Digisum (CC601) conductivity bridge at RT. The X-ray photoelectron spectra were recorded on a V.G. Scientific ESCA 3MKII electron spectrometer. The MgK α X-ray line (1253.6 eV) was used for photoexcitation. The Cu2P_{3/2} (BE = 932.8 $\pm$ 0.2) and Au4f_{7/2} (BE = 83.8 $\pm$ 0.1) lines were used to calibrate the instrument and Ag3d_{5/2} (BE = 368.2) was used for cross checking. All the spectra were recorded using the same spectrometer parameter of 50 eV pass energy and 4 mm slit width. The reduced full width at half maximum (FWHM) at the Au4f_{7/2} (BE = 83.8 eV) level under these conditions was 1.2 eV.

Acknowledgement

The authors thanks, Head, Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad, for facilities.

References

- 1 A Syamal and M M Singh, *Asian J Chem Rev*, 1993, **4**, 89, S Srivastava and D Singh, *Asian J Chem*, 1999, **11**, 1054
- 2 C P Tivedi, R Vyas, D Jain and P Kapoor, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1990, **67**, 871, N R Champness, C S Frampton, G Reid and D A Tocher, *J Chem Soc Dalton Trans*, 1994, 3031, Viendra Joshi, S K Jain and N K Kaushik, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1993, **70**, 997, K R Adam, L F Lindoy, B W Skelton, S V Smith and A H White, *J Chem Soc, Dalton Trans*, 1994, 3361, V V Zeleatsov, *Russ J Coord Chem*, 1996, **22**, 674
- 3 A Kriza, L Pricop and N Stanica, *U P B Bull Sci*, 2000, **B62**, 61 (*Chem Abstr*, 179186)
- 4 W J Geary, *Coord Chem Rev*, 1971, **7**, 81
- 5 M R Mohoud and M T El-Haty, *J Inorg Nucl Chem*, 1980, **42**, 349
- 6 S Srivastava, *Appl Spectrosc Rev*, 1986, **22**, 401
- 7 A Kriza, L Pricop, A Meghea and N Stanica, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 2001, **78**, 448